

Improving the Pedagogical Cooperation of Civil Society Institutions in Enhancing the Socio-Political Activity of Adolescents in Families

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Abstract

This article observes the political motives and values of the young generation, their electoral preferences. It also discusses that the state can effectively implement youth policy, only in the case of teenagers themselves, youth, children's public organizations and other institutions of civil society participate based on pedagogical cooperation.

Keywords: socio-political activeness, activeness in the field of elections, political process, activeness in the field of politics, individual activeness.

Introduction

Attempts to scientifically substantiate the problem of socio-political activity of adolescents from conceptual positions have been made several times in both foreign and local political science. The first studies considering youth activity from the perspective of social and age characteristics appeared in global practice in the early 20th century and correspond to the psychoanalytic approach. Later, from this position, youth began to be viewed as a social category needing support from the state and society during the periods of overcoming certain stages of their development, through which they search for themselves and their place in life.

Youth can be viewed as an active subject of socio-political relations, developed within the framework of cultural approaches, possessing its own norms and values. In this regard, I.M. Ilyinsky's humanistic concept considers youth as an active subject of socio-political relations [135]. The essence of the concept's provisions is that youth, as both the object and subject of the socialization process, acquires subjectivity in the process of realizing their interests, increases the level of self-organization, and, moreover, youth possesses immense intellectual potential and is, therefore, considered the most important social resource of the state.

Main Part

According to the author, youth should be given opportunities for self-organization, self-determination, self-awareness, self-affirmation, and self-development. The emergence of such a concept has led to reconsidering the understanding of the position and role of youth in social life, establishing youth as a subject of social influence. The humanistic principle was the defining

characteristic of conceptual works on youth in the 1980s and early 1990s. The relevance of the theoretical principles of this direction remains at present.

At various times, some works examined youth activity from the perspective of the status of an active member of society acquired through assimilation of social roles and norms, within the framework of the structural and functional approach. Based on this approach in pedagogy, the stratification approach developed, which is actively used by the state to periodize the age of youth. According to current legislation in the Russian Federation, youth age is defined as 14-30 years, while in Uzbekistan, it is considered 18-30 years. Such average age criteria for defining the youth social group are necessary for state bodies to develop state policies targeted at youth.

In general, the stratification approach in studying youth issues is very promising, as it allows us to observe the dynamics of political behavior of youth in certain age periods, compare the tendencies of political preferences among different age groups of youth, as well as identify factors influencing the socio-political level and create conditions for correcting the activities and behaviors of youth of a certain age.

In the context of modern realities, the active integration of adolescents into the political sphere has determined the formation of an appropriate political science approach to studying youth issues in social sciences. Its foundation was laid in the mid-20th century by American scientists S. Verba, N. Nie, and J. Kim in their attempts to propose a model of citizens' political participation, which later became the classical theory of political activity for various categories of the population, including youth [130].

Later, the topic of youth activity was developed in the works of many foreign researchers. G. Marcuse dealt with the problems of political alienation of the younger generation, showing the variety of reasons leading to this social phenomenon and its many forms of manifestation in society [67]; F. Tenbruck supported the distinction of issues related to the socially conditioned development of the younger generation [131]; P. Sack emphasized, based on studies of subjective-objective relations between youth and society, the intellectual, moral, and social maturation of youth [132]; E. Spranger in his research focused on issues of educating youth and emphasized the significant role of youth policy [129].

In the 1990s and early 21st century, new dominants emerged in the works of foreign and local scientists, related to the third wave of democratization, prompted by the transition of post-socialist states to capitalist development. During this period, the focus of political science debates was on the political behavior of youth. The political motives and values of the younger generation were analyzed, their electoral preferences examined, forecasts for future election campaigns were made, common characteristics in the political participation models of various age groups of youth were identified, and the level of youth protest potential was evaluated.

Within political science, the phenomenon of the socio-political activity of youth is traditionally considered in the context of youth-related state policy. At present, this scientific direction is represented by scientific and practical research in the fields of public administration and social management.

Representatives of the first direction define state youth policy as the state's activities aimed at creating guarantees and conditions for the self-realization of young individuals and the development of youth movements and initiatives. They emphasize that the state has the largest resources for a comprehensive youth policy, therefore measures to develop the socio-political activity of youth are the absolute prerogative of state structures, implemented as a holistic and systematic activity of the

state towards the population aged 18 to 30 years. From this point of view, youth policy is a key element of youth policy pursued by society, with political parties, socio-political associations, and other organized social forces competing to shape and implement it.

Within the framework of the state administration direction, there is an understanding of the content of methods and forms of working with youth, characterized by close institutional ties with the state, while youth policy outside it loses an essential part of its content. Although this approach very accurately reflects modern realities (primarily the resource power of the state), it is unsustainable, as the activities of regional structures that influence the solution of youth problems officially remain beyond the scope of youth issues. Moreover, the process of involving civil society institutions, primarily youth associations and unions, in the socio-political activation of youth is being devalued. Although this may not seem significant today, considering the weakness of the latter, in the future, an approach based on understanding the sphere of working with youth can contribute to its one-sided interpretation.

Advocates of the social management direction prioritize non-state institutions in the development of socio-political activity of adolescents. From this point of view, youth policy is a system of ideas and views on youth, their role in social development, as well as the actions of civil society institutions that help translate these views and ideas into social life. This definition emphasizes a high level of self-organization of youth capable of independently overcoming life difficulties and participating in political decision-making.

Within this direction, public organizations, political parties, representative structures in public administration, mass media, and informal associations act as the main subjects aimed at developing socio-political activity.

Each of these social forces has different resources and capabilities, depending on which they create a model of youth policy. However, despite the willingness of actors representing civil society institutions to actively participate in the implementation of youth policy, they themselves are mainly limited by legal, organizational, financial, and human resources, which weakens the social management direction in youth activity issues.

In national youth science, based on the state administration and social management directions of the political science approach, a new perspective has emerged today on the process of developing the socio-political activity of adolescents as a joint activity of state institutions and civil society carried out on a partnership basis. The theoretical aspects of studying the socio-political activity of adolescents through the pedagogical cooperation of state authorities and civil society institutions are described in the works of numerous authors.

From the perspective of pedagogical cooperation, the process of developing the socio-political activity of adolescents should be implemented within the framework of youth policy, representing a system of state measures aimed at creating opportunities and conditions for youth to realize themselves effectively and use their resources for their own benefit. Youth policy can be effectively implemented by the state only if adolescents themselves, youth and children's public organizations, and other civil society institutions participate on the basis of pedagogical cooperation.

According to researchers with this perspective, developing the socio-political activity of adolescents requires studying the formation of civil society institutions, primarily public associations, as actors with great potential and opportunities for influencing the younger generation.

Conclusion

In our opinion, today in our country there is a clear need to create conditions that combine life energy aimed at personal self-realization with the active involvement of various strata of the population in public life. From this point of view, civic associations are created to form human capital, which forces democracy to work.

The activities of civil society institutions are aimed at creating formal and informal communication networks between the state-political system and civil society. Non-governmental organizations are a unique mechanism for involving individuals in the processes of political and civic participation. They divide the public into strong social groups capable of influencing state policy. Civil society institutions help establish a balance between the rights and duties of young citizens, as well as an optimal balance of freedom and responsibility of individuals within a democratic state.

In the context of strengthening the power vertical and the increasing role of civil society institutions, on the one hand, and the development and implementation of youth policy on the basis of pedagogical cooperation, on the other, this approach is considered the most promising for modern education. We use this approach as the methodological basis for our research, specifically in considering forms of expressing the socio-political activity of adolescents in families.

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